

SECURING CASH TRANSACTIONS ANYWHERE USING ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE

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Abstract- Aim of this paper is to propose an enhanced feature to improve the service of Smart Card transactions in less time with more. This is very much helpful in meeting their needs. This research is to combine the money transaction procedure by ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE for safe banking at shopping malls, and other public places, by this we can get rid of hacking which is the major cause arising using smart cards for transactions.

I. INTRODUCTION

Banks are used to create credit by accepting deposits from public. They are also used to transfer money from one account to another. We can transfer the money by making use of banking transaction services like ATM, debit card or credit card, net banking, mobile banking and many more. We aren't sure that if the money transferred from our account to other person is done correctly or not. It also has many security issues. By making use of Artificial Intelligence, we can make the system more secure. Many countries have already introduced A.I. in banking industry for enhancing customer experience, risk management, security. We will be mainly focusing on the threats involved in ATM to withdraw our money which can be resolved by using Artificial Intelligence. Artificial Intelligence can be used to customize (ATM) transactions and surveillance, monitor compliance history of the customers while extending credit. Artificial Intelligence can identify using patterns of customers by recognizing the time of using banking service, device used in transaction, area of transaction, transaction type done by the user. To withdraw the money from our account, we need to visit ATM machines nearby waiting in the queue for our turn to come. If a person wants to withdraw some money readily, waiting in the queue is a big problem for him. There are even chances of malfunctioning of the ATM machines in many cases. Even when we go through all this process, we aren't sure if the personal details of our account are safe and secure or not. More than 1.5 million ATM machines are installed worldwide. In 2014-15, about 40,000 ATM machines are installed only in India. Even though many ATM machines are installed all over the country, many don't function properly and it takes huge amount of time to withdraw the money with increasing number of users. We also need to select options which are not of great use like language, account type, etc compared to the software for transaction of money using Artificial Intelligence. This software is to be installed in all the public places so that no one needs to visit ATM machines to withdraw the money.

II. THREATS INVOLVING USAGE OF ATM CARDS

ATM attacks and fraud continue to make headlines, despite the fact that the technology running ATM networks is becoming more secure and consumer are perhaps more vigilant than ever. Far from being a simple smash-and-grab problem, ATM owners have to be vigilant against different types of threats to ensure they are protecting themselves and their customers. Some of the ATM frauds are usage of duplicate ATM's, card[1] skimming, card trapping, transaction reversal fraud, physical attacks, logical attacks, cash trapping[3].

Figure 1. Card Skimming of figure-1.

Fraudsters use duplicate ATMs that uses software which records the passwords typed on those machines. Thereafter, duplicate cards are manufactured and money is withdrawn with the use of stolen passwords[3]. Card skimming remains the number one threat globally but that is on the wane. Skimming refers to the stealing of electronic card data, enabling the criminal to counterfeit the card.

Figure 2. Card trapping of figure-2.

Consumers experience a normal ATM transaction and are usually unable to notice a problem until their account is defrauded. Card trapping[4] is stealing of

physical card itself through a device fixed to the ATM. In a pre-EMV or chip-and-signature environment, the PIN does not need to be compromised. Again, contactless capability can help.

For example,

NCR helped launch world's first tap and pin

ATM with ANZ using SelfServ 23 and EMV contactless technology. Transaction Reversal Fraud (TRF) involves the creation of an error that makes it appear as though he cash had not been dispensed. The account is re-credited the amount 'withdrawn' but to the criminal pockets. Logical attacks are becoming major and growing attack vector, and one that has potential to cause large amounts of losses. In this type of attack, external electronic devices, or malicious software is used in the crime. The tools are used to allow the criminal to take physical control of the ATM dispenser to withdraw money, which is often called "cash-out"[4]

Figure 3. Logical Attack of figure-3 .

III. PROPOSAL:

The proposal not only deals with the atm machines but also for doing cash transactions anywhere without using atm cards. We have seen many security threats associated with the ATM card. To solve the security threats and satisfy the customers, we have introduced a software using Artificial Intelligence which need to be installed in all the public places, to save time. To transfer the money from our account to another account, AI transaction process has three different user identification methods which can be used in various combinations and sequences depending up on user requirement. The user identification methods are face recognition, finger print sensing technology and OTP. We can use this software using face detection, OTP and finger print sensing technology to logging in to our account and not by withdrawing the money and paying the cash through hand. We can pay by credit

card basis by it has some security issues like we can't notice fake credit cards if there are long line of customers, overlooking and accepting the cards with missing signatures, storing .customer credit card data to charge later and cash refunding. This software is safe, secure and satisfies the customers. It asks the user to login to his account by face detection and finger print sensing and OTP.

For the face recognition, initially the user has the train the system using machine learning to work efficiently, ever successful transaction add us as training set for the system to improve the face recognition system. When the user is about to make a transaction, he has to face the camera and it captures three different instances in three different instances and transmit it to the server in encrypted form. After the image is enhanced the image is detected and the face is recognised and is mapped in to respective account.

When the account of the user is detected, the finger print scanner scans the finger print of the user and authenticates it. The user has to enter the amount that has to be paid and the AI payment system transfers the respective amount to the respective user.

If there is any failure in face recognition or finger print scanner due to hardware failure or software inefficiency, then OTP can replace either face recognition or finger print scanner.

The OTP is sent to the user's mobile number and email address. If the user can't access his mobile phone or email, then he can use emergency codes provided to his account. Emergency codes are the codes which can be given to the users in a set which can be used instead of OTP. Each of the emergency code can be used only once. When he runs out of emergency codes, he has to regenerate them again.

IV. WORKING MODEL OF PRESENT ATM TRANSACTION SYSTEM:

As we entered into ATM we start keeping card with doing certain operations like inserting card, selecting language, and finally entering PIN which may or may not secured. As soon as entering PIN selecting transaction options to with draw the cash, and after many operations finally cash is withdrawn[2].

Figure.4-Present cash Transaction working model.(ATM's).

V. WORKING MODEL OF CASH TRANSACTION USING A.I:

Figure.5-Working model of cash transaction using A.I.

This transaction is going to work under ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE where the user needs to give his face detection, finger print and Account details. In the next Fig.5 it shows the working procedure of cash transaction using artificial intelligence.

VI. DISADVANTAGES OF USING THE PRESENT BANKING SYSTEM

Hacking may take place by keeping web camera above the keyboard of ATM machine. Need to remember the pin. Amount may etcutbytransferring the money from oneAccount to another.Need to wait in the queue near ATM machines. Distracting the users by asking the OTP's sent to user's mobile if online transactions can be seen. If the user is in hurry, he may forget taking his ATM card out of the machine and may leave . The users need to have patience as he need to select various options before entering the required amount to draw from his account[5]. Sometimes, if the user's ATM card doesn't work, then he need to visit the bank. Robbing in ATMS by harming ATM machines and Security guards too[5].

VII. ADVANTAGES OF CASH TRANSACTION BY A.I. SOFTWARE:

It is secure as it has new face recognition and finger print sensor and also OTP and image of the person logged in is sent to the mail and mobile of the user which helps in identifying the intruder easily. This software can be installed anywhere and we don't need to pay cash by using it. Amount is transferred to the owner's account by just logging in to our account and

entering the required amount of cash to pay. We don't need to remember any passwords and pins. Location and other details of where the transaction is done is sent to the user's mobile number as soon as transaction is done.

CONCLUSION

The purpose of introducing this software is to get more secure for presently going transactions by ATM cards are beingsuspected by hacking that exposed card and PIN details to malware at the back-end. Many security attacks occurred and may occur by using the present system. Time of India newspaper exposed the security attacks and stated that 32 lakh debit cards have been compromised to be the biggest ever in India. The breach reportedly originated due to malware in Hitachi Payment Service which allowed hackers to steal information and funds, notably SBI and HDFC banks which are world hit issuing banks.

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